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Studying innovation with patents and machine learning algorithms: a laboratory for engineering students

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ABSTRACT

Teaching innovation management to engineers is becoming increasingly relevant. However, it can be difficult to involve engineers in a discipline in which technical competences do not represent the core whereas professional and soft skills play a critical role. For this reason, adopting the proper teaching approach is key to capture the students' attention and interest. In our study, we propose a laboratory for teaching innovation based upon two elements that are very closed to the engineering mindset: patents and machine learning algorithms.

The laboratory proposes the application of machine learning approaches to patents data, for studying the innovation activity of companies. Three machine learning algorithms, Least Squares, Deep Neural Networks and Decision Trees are exploited. Their application is proposed to capture the relationships between relevant patents output variables (such as, for example, the number of forward citations, as proxy of the company's innovation capability) and the related input features (such as, for example, the number and type of patent technological classes).

By practically using this approach, students can be introduced to some relevant topics in innovation management, such as investments, protection, market identification, cumulation of knowledge.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Teaching innovation management to engineers is becoming increasingly relevant. However, it can be difficult to involve engineers in a discipline in which technical engineering competences do not represent the core and professional and soft skills are more relevant. For this reason, adopting the proper teaching approach is key to capture the students' attention and interest.

2 LITERATURE BACKGROUND

2.1 Teaching innovation management to engineers

The literature on teaching innovation to engineers has received a great attention in the last years, as engineers very often are key actors in innovation processes, both in public and private organisations. Therefore, the educational role of engineering schools is increasingly relevant [1], as they have the task to train such (future) engineers with the proper set of skills and competences. To this aim, technical competences are to be complemented with managerial competences and with soft and professional skills, such as team-working, leadership, creativity, curiosity, autonomy [2]. Integrating this complex mix of technical, managerial and professional competences and skills is not easy: there is a pedagogical issue there, concerning the need to change the focus from theory to practice [13], to care about “how” to teach and not only about “what” to teach [14], to match with the learning style of today's generations [15]. An important suggestion found in the literature to answer to this pedagogical issue is the adoption of active learning approaches, such as, among others, problem-based learning and project-based learning. In fact, these approaches stimulate the acquisition of inquiry skills and the integration of theoretical knowledge, by engaging students in solving ill-defined, open-ended, interdisciplinary problems [3]. More recently, also simulation-based learning (SBL) has been proposed to teach innovation, as engineering students may strongly benefit from the involvement in a real-world environment [4]. For the same reason, the literature suggests the direct involvement of the industry when teaching innovation management to engineers, in order to propose managerial issues in their technological context. For example, Costello [4] suggests bringing entrepreneurs to work together with students within courses on innovation management and shows that this is very much appreciated by students. In summary, three main suggestions come from the above literature: the adoption of active learning approaches, the involvement of actors from the industry environment, the need for multidisciplinary.

2.2 Patents and innovation management

Patents represent a rich and valuable source of information concerning invention and innovation at a global level. Furthermore, patents represent a relevant source of information because of public availability, limited cost of retrieval, reliability, formalization and standardization of the data and information embedded, historical data availability, rich content. For these reasons, patents have been widely studied in literature not only as tools for protecting innovations, but also as tools for investigating

the innovation activity of public and private organizations [5] [9], [7]. In this last case, the literature usually refers to the concept of “Patent Intelligence”. Patent Intelligence can assist innovation managers in decision making processes, providing useful information and data concerning the technological and competitive environment, in terms of threats and opportunities. Given the wide, historical, standardized availability of patents data and information, patent intelligence can exploit even sophisticated, quantitative typologies of elaborations and analyses [5]. This is especially true in the era of the 4th Industrial revolution, in which sophisticated algorithms, such as machine learning ones, able to analyse complex, nonlinear and noisy data, are becoming widely diffused, thanks to the increased computational capacity and to the availability of Big Data. Neural networks are well suited tools to extract significant and useful information from that kind of data [6]. Recently, the use of these tools has been extended in the field of management and especially in the development of business research and innovation analysis, because of their capacity to provide accurate predictions, much better than traditional econometric analyses. Nevertheless, as reported by Lee et al. [7], the application of neural networks in the innovation field is still in an emerging state.

Starting from this background, in this paper a laboratory is proposed, based upon the use of patents and machine learning algorithms, aimed at stimulating the interest of engineers towards the management of innovation and providing them with some of the critical competences and skills in this field.

3 THE PROPOSED LABORATORY ON PATENTS AND MACHINE LEARNING

3.1 The idea

The idea is to exploit patents and machine learning approaches, which are very coherent with the engineers’ technical spirit and values, to teach innovation management, a topic not traditionally included within engineering curricula. In literature, an approach with patents and machine learning algorithms has been proposed recently by Ponta et al. [8]. These authors have employed three machine learning algorithms, Least Squares, Deep Neural Networks and Decision Trees, to a large set of patents data, for studying the innovation capability of companies (IC) and the factors that influence such capability, i.e. the determinants. Patent forward citations are used as proxy of IC (as suggested in [9], [7]), and patent features (e.g., backward citations, number and the type of technological classes) as proxy of IC determinants. IC is taken as the output variable and the patent features as input variables.

The approach proposed by Ponta et al. [8] has been exploited to build a laboratory on the management of innovation, giving the opportunity to discuss with students about some of the most relevant concepts and issues in the management of innovation: the innovation capability and its determinants, how they relate each other and how they can be measured, the role of patents, the investments in innovation, the cumulation of knowledge, the identification of markets for innovation.

3.2 The methodology

The idea described above has been discussed with four groups of stakeholders, separately: teachers of innovation management within an engineering school, students of industrial engineering, engineers working in the field of innovation and intellectual property, and institutional stakeholders, namely the Rector and the Dean of the Engineering School. The synthesis of the discussion process is given in table 1:

Table 1. Building a proposal: stakeholders involved

Stakeholders (n. and type)	Topics of discussion	Needs, issues and suggestions emerged
2 engineers working in the field of innovation and IP management	What are the competences needed for an engineer involved in innovation processes; how engineers within companies usually behave when involved in innovation processes: positive and negative aspects	Competences needed: IP tools and IP strategy; managerial issues and tools in the innovation process. Need for engagement and culture in IP
4 teachers of innovation management	How engineers usually behave when involved in courses on innovation management: positive and negative aspects; what are the basic topics for an engineer to be able to effectively contribute to innovation processes	Students are lost with qualitative topics; need to mix technical and managerial competences and soft skills; managerial topics are appreciated only when specifically connected to technology. The management of IP is badly perceived, it is considered as a legal topic
3 industrial engineering Students	How students perceive innovation management topics; main problems in acquiring competences in the management of technology; how they perceive innovation management with respect to their main technology studies	IP management is too legal; difficult to connect IP with managerial and technological topics; innovation management is a topic too fuzzy, not enough systematized, too qualitative
2 institutional stakeholders (Rector and Dean of Engineering school)	What is the role of the University and of the Engineering School in training engineers for innovation management; how to integrate technical courses with managerial ones; how to integrate technical competences with professional skills	Need to invest in topics concerning innovation and IP; need for interdisciplinary and soft skills for engineers; experiential learning as a fundamental tool for integration of different competences and skills; need for a direct involvement of companies

After having collected all the comments and suggestions from these stakeholders, a version of the proposed laboratory has been defined and is being proposed to students.

3.3 The proposed laboratory

The proposed laboratory, as resulting after the interaction and discussion with the four categories of stakeholders, is synthesised in table 2. The laboratory is organised around a real case, involving a company responsible for proposing a managerial issue that could be supported by patent analyses. This is important to give students a real ground to play in, with a clear technical environment to delve into. The laboratory could be adapted (and offered) to engineers coming from whatever discipline, by choosing the company and the case in coherence with the students' specific discipline.

Table 2. A laboratory on patents, innovation and machine learning algorithms

Module	Topics	Time (hours)	Place
1	Inventions, innovations, patented innovations	3	A company, in co-teaching with the R&D or Innovation manager and / or with the IP manager of the company
	Using patents as a strategic weapon	3	
2	Patents, big data and machine learning methods	6	University
	Machine learning methods applied in the field of innovation management: the measurement and prediction of the Innovation Capability of companies	6	University
4	Project work: applying machine learning approaches to patents data	8	Working with a company tutor on a specific topic / issue / objective, concerned with innovation management, proposed by the company. For example, predicting the innovation activity of competitors
5	Discussion of the projects results	4	University, inviting the involved companies or the Company
For a 10-15 people class, one "leading company" is involved hosting module 1 and proposing 1 project for applying machine learning approaches to patents and innovation (module 4). Three groups of students are created, competing on the same project: the best project will be awarded after the final discussion that could be held at LIUC or in the hosting company.			

1 or 2 tutors are necessary for supporting students during their project work.

A patent database, allowing for efficient data search and download is necessary (e.g. Orbit).

A tool for supporting artificial intelligence modelling is necessary (e.g. Matlab).

A first module, lasting 6 hours, is dedicated to the basic concepts of innovation, innovation management and patents, not in general, purely theoretical terms, but applied to the real context of a company. The involvement of the company's R&D or Innovation manager and of the Intellectual Property manager is crucial.

A second module, lasting around 16 hours, is dedicated to the explanation of some (basic) machine learning algorithms and to the realisation of some real applications, as for example those reported in Ponta et al. [8]. It is important here to merge knowledge about the algorithms with examples of applications in the real context of innovation.

The third module, lasting 8 to 16 hours (depending on the availability of the company) is dedicated to an application of machine learning approaches, with patent data, for supporting decision making around a specific innovation problem, proposed by the company. Just to make a few examples:

- The company identifies a set of relevant competitors and asks students to investigate (and predict) the innovation capability of the selected group of companies, testing and evaluating the various appropriate machine learning algorithm(s) in coherence with the type and amount of data available;
- The company identifies a specific patent variable to be investigated (taken as output variable, for example, the number of patents) and asks students to identify the patent input variables able to predict the selected output variable, selecting and applying the most appropriate machine learning algorithm(s) to the most appropriate set of patent data.

The fourth module is dedicated to the presentation and discussion of the students' projects. An evaluation committee composed by the company's R&D or Innovation manager, the IP manager, the university lecturer and the projects tutor(s) must be involved. The best project will be awarded by the Company. The final assessment will be based upon the judgment of the committee, in which different aspects will be considered: (i) knowledge about (and confidence with) the topics of IP, innovation management, application of machine learning algorithms; (ii) presentation ability; (ii) teamworking; (iv) accuracy and precision of the results achieved; (v) coherence and usefulness of the results for the company's needs.

As a whole, the proposed laboratory would introduce students to some relevant topics in innovation management, such as: the relevance and role of patents; the actual use of patents by companies; the use of patents to measure the innovation performance of companies and the drivers of a good innovation performance; the protection of

innovation; the companies' investments in innovation and patents; the link among innovation, patents and markets; the effects of internationalisation on innovation strategic decisions; the relevance of cumulation of knowledge for successful innovation.

A beta version of the laboratory will be offered to industrial engineers in academic year 2019-2020, in order to define a final version to be proposed since 2020-2021.

In order to move from the beta version to the final one, a survey will be conducted at the end of the first release, involving all the four types of stakeholders, in order to evaluate the results achieved, the weaknesses and the strengths of the proposed laboratory. The stakeholders will be asked about whether the laboratory has helped in answering to the needs and issues emerged during the discussion (reported in table 1). This first release would also bring into evidence potential issues in group profiling and in group selection, to be considered for the final use of the laboratory.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The proposed laboratory is expected to give positive contributions from both a practical and theoretical perspective.

4.1 Expected benefits for the engineering community

From the point of view of the engineering community, including both students and professionals, the proposed laboratory is expected to:

- stimulate the interest on innovation management and patents, topics recognised in the literature as particularly relevant for future engineers to play their role in society [10], [1];
- provide companies with a professional profile which is very useful and not diffused yet (especially in Italy), characterised by competences on patents and their use for supporting the management of innovation. This important benefit has been underlined with great emphasis by the stakeholders coming from the industry environment, who ask for a larger use of patents among engineers;
- provide an opportunity to strengthen links between industry and university, another key element in the curriculum of future engineers [4], thus offering students the opportunity to create a network with companies, potentially useful for their future professional life;
- improve the students' "soft" and "professional" skills, by engaging them in project-based learning and teamworking, by stimulating them within a competition, by embedding their work in a real-world context, by asking them a formal presentation of their work and by involving people from outside the university environment in their evaluation [3];
- offer students the opportunity to directly exploit systems and tools that are becoming increasingly relevant in the era of the 4th industrial revolution, such as artificial intelligence;

- collect a set of projects and companies' cases, by repeating the laboratory over time, which may represent teaching material to be exploited in future classes on the management of innovation.

4.2 Contribution to theory

From a theoretical perspective, the proposed laboratory will hopefully give a contribution to the literature on teaching innovation to engineers, a key topic for engineering schools [11]. In terms of contents, the laboratory suggests an original integration of innovation topics with artificial intelligence topics, of patents and IT, thus providing for a multidisciplinary approach, which is highly recommended in literature [10]. In terms of methodology, the laboratory is based upon three pillars: (i) active learning approach with a project-based activity, necessary to stimulate students towards an entrepreneurial approach in their work [12]; (ii) teamwork, necessary for developing soft skills such as leadership and relational abilities; (iii) quantitative analyses (with the support of appropriate tools), with a typical engineering approach. The mix of contents and methodology that characterises the proposed laboratory can be considered particularly useful for teaching innovation in the era of the 4th industrial revolution.

A contribution could also be given to the theory on patent intelligence, as new models of analysis and new cases can be developed through the activities conducted by students. This could be particularly relevant because of the exploitation of algorithms of machine learning, which are not yet widely diffused in the field [7].

The applications studied during the laboratory can also be interesting for the scientific community working on artificial intelligence, machine learning, data science. In fact, the analyses conducted allow to understand the advantages and limits of the different methods and tools of AI in a specific context of application: innovation management and patents.

4.3 Limits and future research

The paper presents several limitations that we plan to manage in our future research. First, the background literature on the pedagogical theories could be significantly enriched in order to better position the proposed laboratory and its results with respect to what suggested and discussed in that literature. Furthermore, some other suggestions aimed at improving the laboratory itself could be drawn from that literature.

Second, after the first “beta version” of the laboratory, some other pedagogical aspects of the laboratory could be studied, especially referring to the teaching and learning activities, the learning resources needed, the criteria for selecting and profiling students for groups formation and management, the assessment methods.

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